

Deliverable 5.4.6 SMP Catalog

A SMP CATALOG FOR THE ENERGY RESEARCH SOFTWARE ENGINEERING
COMMUNITY
19.12.2025

A SMP Catalog for the Energy Research Software Engineering Community

Corinna Seiwert ⁵

¹Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, ROR, Chair of Computer Science 7 (Computer Networks and Communication Systems), Martensstraße 3, 91058 Erlangen

²OFFIS, Institute for Information Technology, ROR, Oldenburg, Germany

³Carl von Ossietzky University of Oldenburg, Department of Computing Science, ROR, Ammerländer Heerstraße 114-118, 26129 Oldenburg

⁴Institute for Automation of Complex Power Systems, RWTH Aachen University, Mathieustraße 10, 52074 Aachen, Germany

⁵Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, ROR, Institute for Automation and Applied Informatics, Hermann-von-Helmholtz-Platz 1, 76344 Eggenstein-Leopoldshafen

⁶University of Freiburg, INATECH, ROR Emmy-Noether-Str. 2, 79110 Freiburg,

Published by

Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, ROR, Chair of Computer Science 7 (Computer Networks and Communication Systems), Martensstraße 3, 91058 Erlangen

Acknowledgements

The authors of this article have used various preparatory works from the NFDI4Energy to create this portrait, and references have been made where possible. Thanks to all those who are not named. The authors would like to thank the German Federal Government, the German State Governments, and the Joint Science Conference (GWK) for their funding and support as part of the NFDI4Energy consortium. The work was funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) – 501865131 within the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI, www.nfdi.de).

License

This document is published under the Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0). This license allows users to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format, so long as attribution is given to the creator. The license allows for commercial use.

Table of Contents

General Information	3
Summary	3
Deliverable within NFDI4Energy	3
Introduction	4
Fundamentals of Software Management Plans	4
Definition and Purpose	4
Typical Components of a SMP	4
General and Technical Information	4
Accessibility, Reuse, and Publication	5
Legal and Ethical Aspects (Intellectual Property and Governance)	5
Long-term Preservation and Archiving	5
Resources and Responsibilities	5
Existing SMP Catalog by the Max Planck Digital Library	6
Application Classes	6
Structure of the Catalog	6
Extending the SMP-Catalogue for the Energy Domain	7
Conclusion	10

General Information

Summary

Software Management Plans (SMPs) are a valuable tool for structuring and systematizing software development within a scientific context. A SMP serves as a document that collects and organizes all relevant aspects of software development, thereby supporting a systematic approach and ensuring compliance with recognized standards and best practices.

Within the NFDI4Energy consortium, we aim to provide the Energy Research Software Engineering community with a SMP that reflects the specific requirements of energy research. In several other NFDI consortia, a SMP developed by the Max Planck Digital Library (MPDL) is already in use; therefore, we have adopted this version as the basis for our work. However, we extended the original MPDL SMP by incorporating additional questions derived from other SMP Catalogs, as well as newly formulated questions that address the particular needs and practices of the energy research domain.

The SMP catalog is available through the RDMO4Energy instance, ensuring accessibility and reusability for the research community.

Deliverable within NFDI4Energy

Within Task Area 5 of the NFDI4Energy consortium, our work focuses on establishing an infrastructure to support software used in energy research. The development of a SMP catalog contributes directly to this goal by providing structured guidance for the creation, documentation, and management of research software. This deliverable supports the Energy Research Software Engineering community in adopting systematic development practices and promotes the long-term sustainability, transparency, and reusability of software-based research outputs.

Introduction

In recent years, research software has become an essential component of modern scientific practice, serving both as a tool for data analysis and as a research output in its own right. Ensuring the sustainability, quality, and reusability of such software has therefore emerged as a critical challenge for the scientific community. To address this, the concept of the Software Management Plan (SMP) has been introduced. A SMP is a living document that collects and structures all relevant aspects of software development within a scientific context, thereby supporting a systematic approach and ensuring compliance with recognized standards [1]. The motivation for implementing SMPs can be understood in four main areas. First, SMPs improve scientific practice and project management by formalizing structures and objectives, clarifying roles and responsibilities, supporting knowledge transfer, and providing mechanisms for quality assurance [2]. Second, research funding organizations are increasingly recognizing the importance of software as a research output. While SMPs are not yet mandatory, several funding bodies, including the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft and the VolkswagenStiftung, have already introduced policies that emphasize sustainable handling and accessibility of research software [1]. Third, SMPs enhance the visibility and impact of research. By ensuring that software can be reused, cited, and archived, they contribute to reproducibility, validation, and the avoidance of redundant work [3]. Finally, SMPs support institutional recognition and the professionalization of research software development. They help to establish research software as a valuable scientific achievement and strengthen the role of Research Software Engineers as key contributors to sustainable scientific practice [1]. In summary, SMPs offer a structured and forward-looking approach to software development in science. They not only facilitate compliance with emerging funding requirements, but also promote quality assurance, sustainability, and the long-term visibility of research contributions.

In this work, we aim to extend a general SMP from the engineering domain and adapt it for the development of energy research software.

Fundamentals of Software Management Plans

Definition and Purpose

A SMP is a living document that structures and supports software development within a scientific project. Its primary purpose is to ensure traceability and long-term usability of research software, thereby contributing directly to quality assurance [1]. A SMP consolidates all relevant information related to the creation, documentation, storage, versioning, licensing, archiving, and/or publication of project-related software. In addition, it may also address requirements for hardware, external libraries, and related outputs such as text or data publications.

SMPs are conceptually similar to *Data Management Plans* (DMPs) for research data. They help overcome short-term challenges in software development, which are often caused by tight deadlines and the realities of academic work. By formalizing structures and objectives, SMPs ensure that research software remains accessible and reusable in the short, medium, and long term. Moreover, SMPs can be closely linked to DMPs, mainly when software is used for generating or processing research data [2].

Typical Components of a SMP

Although templates may vary in scope and emphasis, the contents of a SMP contain these core areas:

General and Technical Information

This section describes the software project and its expected outputs. It typically includes:

- **Software products:** What software artifacts (including documentation and supplementary materials) are to be produced?

- **Responsibilities:** Who is responsible for approving or releasing the software (e.g., project leader, lead developer)?
- **Dependencies:** Which external software, tools, models, or libraries are used, and under which licenses?
- **Development and quality assurance:** Which development model is applied, and how is code correctness verified (e.g., through testing or code reviews)?

Accessibility, Reuse, and Publication

This section outlines how the software will be made accessible to others and how reuse will be facilitated:

- **Code repositories:** Where is the code hosted (e.g., GitHub, GitLab)? Is the repository public or private?
- **Release management:** How are releases planned and distributed (frequency, decision-making process)?
- **Version control:** Which system is consistently used by the team (e.g., Git)?
- **Documentation and Readability :** How will the code be documented and made understandable (e.g., coding standards, automated documentation, peer reviews)?
- **Citations:** How will the software be made citable and easily referenced in scientific work?

Legal and Ethical Aspects (Intellectual Property and Governance)

Legal considerations are crucial for sustainable software use:

- **Licensing:** Which license will be applied to the developed software? Is it compatible with third-party licenses and acceptable to all project partners?
- **Governance model:** Does the project have a governance structure regulating decision-making?
- **Third-party rights:** Are there patents, copyrights, or other intellectual property restrictions to observe?

Long-term Preservation and Archiving

To guarantee usability beyond the project's lifetime, this section addresses:

- **Archiving:** Where will the software be preserved in the long term (e.g., institutional repositories)?
- **Dependencies:** How will specific and implicit dependencies (e.g., operating systems, SDKs, browsers) be documented?
- **External services:** Does the software depend on external services (e.g., web APIs or databases) that may change or disappear?

Resources and Responsibilities

This area considers organizational and personnel aspects:

- **Roles and responsibilities:** Who is responsible for development, project management, support, and maintenance?
- **Resource planning:** How much time and funding are allocated for software development and support?

- **Knowledge transfer:** How is expertise preserved within the project team (e.g., pair programming, documentation, regular reviews)?
- **Plan updates:** How often will the SMP be reviewed and revised?

The level of detail in a SMP should be proportional to the size and complexity of the project. For small-scale projects, a brief section may suffice, while larger and long-term research projects may require comprehensive and detailed plans extending over several pages [1], [2].

Existing SMP Catalog by the Max Planck Digital Library

The foundation for our work is an existing SMP catalog developed by the Max Planck Digital Library (MPDL) in 2022 and maintained in a public Git repository by the Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO) [4] community. This repository contains content objects such as catalogs, attributes, options, conditions, views, and tasks that can be directly used with the DMP software RDMO. In this way, the SMP builds upon established tools and infrastructures that are already widely applied in research data management.

The SMP catalog is designed to be domain-independent and provides a structured set of questions that cover the most important aspects of research software management. During its development, the FAIR4RS principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable for Research Software) were explicitly considered, ensuring that the catalog not only supports project-specific requirements but also aligns with community standards for sustainable and reusable research software.

Application Classes

A central concept of the SMP is its division into application classes, which define the scope and criticality of the software under development [5]. Depending on the assigned application class, a project will be presented with a corresponding number of questions, ranging from minimal requirements for personal use to comprehensive planning for critical, product-like software. The four application classes are defined as follows:

- **Application Class 0:** Software is intended for *personal use* with a very limited scope. No distribution within or outside the institution is planned.
- **Application Class 1:** Software is developed in a *limited context* but is intended for *broader use and further development* beyond purely personal purposes.
- **Application Class 2:** Software is designed for *long-term development and maintainability*, serving as a foundation for transitioning into *product-level status*.
- **Application Class 3:** Software must *minimize errors and reduce risks*, which is essential for *critical software* or projects with *product-like characteristics*.

This classification enables a flexible adaptation of the SMP to the size, complexity, and sustainability requirements of individual software projects.

Structure of the Catalog

The SMP catalog is organized into a set of overarching sections that reflect key dimensions of software development and management. These sections ensure a comprehensive treatment of both technical and organizational aspects:

- General Information
- Software Project Partner(s)
- Software Project Schedule
- Software Project Management
- Software Development Requirements
- Code
- Third Party Components and Libraries
- Infrastructure
- Preservation
- Security
- Governance and Defined Processes
- Documentation
- Testing
- Releasing
- Public Availability
- Metadata
- Support
- Intellectual Property Rights
- License
- Dual Use

By covering these dimensions, the SMP supports project teams in systematically addressing software development challenges while ensuring compliance with quality, governance, and sustainability standards.

The catalog is currently being adopted and used within NFDI4Ing, where it forms the baseline for software management planning across different engineering disciplines.

Extending the SMP-Catalogue for the Energy Domain

Since software plays a major role in energy systems research, we aim to provide a SMP within the RDMO4Energy¹ instance. The SMP developed by the MPDL is already used by several other NFDI consortia, which is why we decided to adopt it as the foundation for our own catalog.

In addition to the MPDL SMP, we reviewed other existing SMP catalogs and selected additional questions relevant to energy research. Furthermore, we developed our own domain-specific questions tailored to the needs of the energy research community.

These newly developed or adapted questions were added to the original SMP catalog by the MPDL, resulting in the NFDI4Energy SMP for Energy Research Software.

The following questions were added or adapted to better support the documentation and management of energy research projects:

¹<https://rdmo.nfdi4energy.org>

- **General**

- *Which user groups and domain communities are the intended audience of the software?*

Specify which user groups and domain communities the software is intended for. This includes both the type of users (e.g., researchers, students, industry partners, general public) and their disciplinary background (e.g., energy systems, engineering, economics, computer science).

Defining the target audience helps clarify functional requirements, usability expectations, documentation needs, and dissemination strategies. Consider whether different user groups may require different levels of detail, interfaces, or support, for example, technical documentation for researchers, simplified interfaces for practitioners, or educational materials for students.

- **Software Project Management**

- *How are the software requirements documented?*

Describe how the functional and non-functional requirements of the software are captured and maintained. This may include requirements specifications, user stories, use cases, or other documentation methods. Clear documentation of requirements ensures that the software development aligns with research objectives and user needs.

- *How are new developers or contributors onboarded, and what processes or materials are provided to support them?*

Describe how new developers or contributors are onboarded into the project. This may include documentation (e.g., onboarding guides, contribution guidelines, coding standards), introductory meetings, mentoring structures, or training materials.

Specify where onboarding materials are stored and which person or role is responsible for maintaining them and supporting new team members during the onboarding process. A clear onboarding plan ensures efficient knowledge transfer, reduces entry barriers, and helps maintain software quality and continuity within the project.

- *How will knowledge and information be preserved if a developer leaves the project?*

Describe the measures taken to retain project knowledge and information in case a developer leaves. This may include maintaining technical documentation, knowledge bases, code comments, handover protocols, or mentoring processes. Structured knowledge management ensures the continuity of software development and reduces dependence on individual contributors.

- **Software Development Requirements**

- *Are there requirements regarding interoperability with other research software or databases?*

Describe whether and to what extent your software needs to interoperate with other research software, simulation tools, or databases. Mention any interfaces, data formats, protocols, or standards (e.g., FMI, SSP, REST, HDF5) that are used to ensure interoperability. Defining these requirements early facilitates integration with existing research infrastructures and supports the reusability of the software.

- **Code**

- *How is software versioning managed?*

Describe how software versioning is organized and documented. Indicate what naming conventions or strategies (e.g., semantic versioning, release tags) are applied, and how changes are tracked. Clear version management improves traceability, team collaboration, and the reproducibility of research results.

- **Computational Environment**

- *Which operating systems are supported by the software?*
Specify the operating systems on which the software is intended to run.
- *Which processor architectures are required or supported by the software?*
Describe the processor architecture(s) required to run the software (e.g., x86_64, ARM, IA64). Indicate whether multiple architectures are supported.
- *What typical hardware is required to run the software?*
Describe the minimal or typical hardware setup required to run the software. Include information about specific devices if required (e.g., GPUs, embedded systems, measurement hardware).
- *What are the minimum and typical memory (RAM) requirements?*
Specify the minimum and recommended memory requirements for running the software under typical conditions.
- *What are the storage requirements of the software?*
Describe how much free storage space is required for installation, execution, and generated outputs.

- **Third Party Components and Libraries**

- *Which third-party datasets or databases will be used?* Describe which external datasets or data retrieved from external databases or web services (e.g., via APIs) are used within your software or simulation.

- **Governance and Defined Processes**

- *How will the software comply with disability accessibility guidelines?*
Describe the measures taken to ensure that the software complies with established accessibility standards (e.g., WCAG, EN 301 549). This may include features such as keyboard navigation, screen reader compatibility, color contrast, alternative text, scalable fonts, or speech support. Considering accessibility improves usability for a broader audience and supports inclusive research practices.

- **Public Availability**

- *How can others contribute to the software?*
Describe how external individuals or organizations can contribute to your software if it is released as open source. Indicate whether contribution guidelines (CONTRIBUTING.md), a code of conduct, issue tracking, or review processes are in place.

- **Metadata**

- *How can users cite your software? Please provide a link to your Software Citation File (CFF) if available.*
Describe how your software should be cited in scientific publications. Indicate whether a CITATION.cff file, a DOI (e.g., via Zenodo, Figshare, or Software Heritage), or a recommended citation text is available. Providing a standardized citation method facilitates academic referencing, supports recognition of software as a research output, and ensures traceability of results.

Since defining the relevant time span of the software is particularly important in the energy domain, we have included this aspect in the question “What is the intended use of the software? How will it contribute to research?”. Accordingly, we added the following guidance to the description:

“Describe whether and to what extent your software needs to interoperate with other research software, simulation tools, or databases. Mention any interfaces, data formats, protocols, or standards

(e.g., FMI, SSP, REST, HDF5) that are used to ensure interoperability. Defining these requirements early facilitates integration with existing research infrastructures and enhances the reusability of the software.”

Additionally, we wanted to address the publication of test results. Therefore, we included the following sentence to the question “Will this software be publicly available?”:

”In this context, please also indicate whether the test procedures and results of the software will be published or otherwise made publicly available. Sharing test results can improve transparency, support reproducibility, and facilitate validation by other researchers.”

These adjustments to the SMP catalog place greater emphasis on the FAIR principles for research software [6] and make it better suited for use in the energy domain.

Conclusion

Research software plays an increasingly important role as a recognized scientific output. To better understand, structure, and document the relevant aspects of research software development, SMPs have been established. SMPs are also recommended by various funding bodies as a means to ensure transparency, sustainability, and reusability of research software.

Within the NFDI4Energy consortium, we aim to provide a SMP catalog that supports the Energy Research Software Engineering community. SMPs typically include general and technical information, address questions on accessibility, reusability, and publication, and cover legal, ethical, and organizational aspects such as long-term preservation, archiving, and the allocation of resources and responsibilities. At the same time, each SMP should always be adapted to the scope and objectives of the respective project.

Several SMP catalogs already exist, with the version developed by MPDL being widely adopted in other NFDI consortia. For this reason, we decided to build upon the MPDL catalog as a foundation for the NFDI4Energy community, extending it with additional questions.

The SMP catalog is provided within the RDMO4Energy instance, ensuring its accessibility and practical use for researchers in the field.

References

- [1] Y. V. Grossmann, G. Lanza, K. Biernacka, T. Hasler, and K. Helbig, “Software management plans – current concepts, tools, and application,” *Data Science Journal*, vol. 23, p. 43, Sep. 10, 2024, ISSN: 1683-1470. DOI: 10.5334/dsj-2024-043. [Online]. Available: <https://datascience.codata.org/articles/10.5334/dsj-2024-043/> (visited on 09/04/2025).
- [2] “Writing and using a software management plan | software sustainability institute.” (), [Online]. Available: <https://www.software.ac.uk/guide/writing-and-using-software-management-plan> (visited on 09/04/2025).
- [3] K. Hartig and V. Soßna, “Forschungsdatenmanagement in DFG-anträgen. was kann, was soll, was muss beschrieben werden? ergebnisse des workshops VI im rahmen der jahrestagung der forschungs- und technologiereferent/innen 2016 am 18./19. februar in potsdam,” Apr. 8, 2016, Publisher: Hannover : Institutionelles Repositorium der Leibniz Universität Hannover. DOI: 10.15488/262. [Online]. Available: <https://repo.uni-hannover.de/handle/123456789/284> (visited on 09/04/2025).
- [4] O. Michaelis, J. Klar, S. Brosig, et al., *Content for Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO)*, version 1.5.0-rdmo-2.0.0, Sep. 2024. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.596706. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog>.
- [5] T. Schlauch, M. Meinel, and C. Haupt, *Dlr software engineering guidelines*, version 1.0.0, Aug. 2018. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1344612. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1344612>.

- [6] N. P. Chue Hong, D. S. Katz, M. Barker, *et al.*, *Fair principles for research software (fair4rs principles)*, version 1.0, May 2022. DOI: 10.15497/RDA00068. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00068>.